

OPTIMIZING THREAD ENGAGEMENT IN PUMP ASSEMBLIES: A FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Thread engagement in pump assemblies is critical in ensuring structural integrity, operational efficiency, and ease of maintenance. However, thread failures, improper engagement, and wear can significantly impact pump performance and reliability, leading to operational downtime and safety risks in critical applications. This study investigates the mechanical implications of reducing thread engagement on pump barrel-head connections within a pump assembly. Specifically, it compares stress distribution and fatigue characteristics between a baseline design (M33X1.5) with six engaged threads and a revised design (M33X1.5 and MJ33X1.5) with five threads. Finite Element Analysis (FEA) was done to evaluate M33X1.5 and MJ33X1.5 thread profiles under nominal (NOM) and least material conditions (LMC). The FEA simulations using ANSYS Mechanical 14.0 analyzed stress distributions and fatigue performance across different loading scenarios. Results indicate that reducing thread engagement from six to five threads increases stresses, particularly at the thread roots, thereby elevating the risk of fatigue failure. The study highlights the effectiveness of optimizing thread geometry, particularly with MJ33X1.5 profiles, in reducing stress and enhancing fatigue resistance. The Goodman diagram analysis confirms that all designs meet safety criteria under cyclic loading conditions, albeit with varying margins. Designs employing MJ series thread profile exhibit superior stress distribution and fatigue performance compared to M series thread profile, emphasizing the importance of thread profile selection in enhancing pump assembly durability. The findings underscore practical implications for pump assembly design and maintenance strategies. Maintaining an adequate number of engaged threads and optimizing thread profiles are crucial for reducing stress and ensuring long-term reliability under operational conditions. While this study provides valuable insights, future research should focus on experimental validation to corroborate FEA findings and explore additional factors, such as dynamic thermal cycles and pressure fluctuations, to assess pump assembly performance comprehensively.

Keywords: Thread Engagement, Pump Assembly, Finite Element Analysis, Pump Barrel-Head Connection, Thread Failure Analysis, Goodman Diagram, Nominal Material Condition, Least Material Condition

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INTRODUCTION

Thread engagement in pump assemblies ensures structural integrity, operational efficiency, and maintenance convenience [1]. Threads facilitate the connection and disconnection of components, allowing easy assembly and disassembly, which is particularly important during the maintenance and repair of pumps. However, thread failures, improper engagement, and wear can significantly affect pump performance and reliability [2]. Thread failures can lead to leaks, pressure loss, and even pump breakdown. In critical applications such as chemical processing or oil and gas, such failures can cause substantial operational downtime, environmental hazards, and safety risks [3]. Improper thread engagement or misalignment can compromise the mechanical stability of the connection, leading to premature wear and eventual failure [4]. Thread wear, caused by repeated mechanical loading, corrosion, or abrasion, reduces the effective lifespan of threaded connections [5]. As threads wear, their ability to maintain a secure, leak-proof connection diminishes, which can result in increased maintenance costs and reduced operational efficiency. Understanding the factors influencing thread performance and implementing appropriate design and material strategies are essential to mitigate these adverse effects and ensure reliable pump operation.

This study investigates the mechanical consequences of reducing thread engagement on pump barrel-head connections in a pump assembly. The research aims to analyze and compare the stress distribution and fatigue characteristics of two design configurations: a baseline design with six engagement threads and a revised design with five threads. In addition to reducing one thread in the revised design, a larger cutout was made at the base of the pump head. The Finite Element Method (FEM) was employed to compute the von Mises and principal stresses in both design configurations, analyzing M33X1.5 and MJ33X1.5 thread profiles in the revised design. Nominal (NOM) and least material condition (LMC) were also considered for the thread profiles to account for manufacturing tolerances. The Goodman diagram was used to evaluate the fatigue performance of the threads. The baseline and revised designs (considering thread type and material conditions) were assessed using their stress values, fatigue characteristics, and the Goodman diagram to understand the impact of reducing thread engagement. This comprehensive analysis provided insights into the structural integrity and durability of the pump assembly under different thread engagement conditions, contributing to optimizing pump head and barrel designs for improved performance and reliability.

The finite element analysis revealed that reducing thread engagement from six to five threads increased stress concentrations, particularly at the thread roots, leading to a higher risk of fatigue failure. Optimizing thread geometry, such as using MJ33X1.5 profiles, mitigated some adverse effects, enhancing stress distribution and fatigue performance. The study suggested prioritizing an adequate number of engaged threads and optimized thread profiles over stringent manufacturing tolerances to maintain reliability.

The findings of this study had significant practical implications for the design and maintenance of pump assemblies. Reducing thread engagement led to higher stress concentrations and reduced fatigue life, potentially compromising the reliability and durability of the pump. The study also compared thread geometries to propose the adverse effects of reducing thread engagement. Additionally, the minimal impact of manufacturing tolerances on stress distribution and fatigue performance suggested that maintaining high precision in thread manufacturing could have been more critical than ensuring an adequate number of engaged threads and optimizing thread geometry. However, adhering to acceptable manufacturing tolerances was essential to prevent unforeseen issues.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Pump threads are subjected to medium to heavy mechanical loads, hydraulic pressures, and environmental factors like corrosion and temperature fluctuations [6]. The mechanical performance of threaded connections is assessed based on load-bearing capacity, fatigue resistance, and wear resistance [7,8]. The choice of thread type and material must align with the expected load conditions to prevent mechanical failure, ensuring threads can endure the operational cycles of the pump without significant wear or fatigue.

FEA has emerged as an essential tool in designing and analyzing the threads used in pump assemblies [9]. FEA simulations compute mechanical stresses, strains, deformation, pressure, and other critical performance aspects of the thread design, thus helping engineers optimize thread designs [10,11]. Common methodologies in FEA of pump threads include structural analysis (static or dynamic loading conditions), fluid dynamics, vibration analysis, thermal analysis, and fatigue analysis [12]. FEA in threads and screws primarily includes structural analysis to compute stress, strain, deformation, fatigue life, and other stimuli. Stress concentrations typically occur at the root of the threads, the most vulnerable points for crack initiation and propagation. Yang et al. (2013) emphasized the need for appropriate load requirements and thread performance to prevent mechanical failure [13]. FEA has also been extensively used to predict the fatigue life of threaded connections [14]. Fatigue analysis computes the number of cycles to failure in response to repeated dynamic loads. Eraslan and İnan (2010) [15] analyzed fatigue failure using different thread profiles (V-thread, buttress, reverse buttress, and square thread). They reported that thread design significantly influences stress concentrations and load transfer efficiency. Specifically, the buttress and reverse buttress threads exhibit more favorable stress distribution. This finding is critical for pumps operating under fluctuating loads, where fatigue failure is common.

The number of engaged threads directly affects the mechanical strength and reliability of the joint. Pai and Hass (2002) [16] showed that increasing the number of engaged threads improved load distribution and reduced stress concentration at individual thread roots. The shape of the screw also impacts mechanical performance and manufacturing ease. Conical screws provided better stress distribution and reduced the risk of thread stripping under axial loads. In contrast, cylindrical screws were easier to manufacture and provided more consistent engagement, suitable for high-precision applications [17].

The Goodman diagram predicts the fatigue life of materials under cyclic loading conditions. It relates the mean stress and alternating stress a material can endure before failure, aiding in the safe design of mechanical components [18]. The x-axis represents mean stress, while the y-axis represents alternating stress. Key points on the Goodman diagram include the ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and the endurance limit. The equation of the Goodman diagram is given by $\frac{\sigma_m}{\sigma_u} + \frac{\sigma_a}{\sigma_e} = 1$, where σ_m is the mean stress, σ_a is the alternating stress, σ_u is the ultimate tensile strength, and σ_e is the endurance limit. The area below the diagram represents the safe region where stresses will not cause fatigue failure, while the above indicates potential failure.

Nominal Material Condition (NOM) and Least Material Condition (LMC) are used to describe different states of a part based on its material limits and tolerances [19,20]. Nominal Material Condition refers to a part's ideal or specified dimension as designed, representing the target dimension without considering any manufacturing tolerances. For instance, if a bolt is designed to have a diameter of 10 mm, the nominal condition is exactly 10 mm. On the other hand, the Least Material Condition is the state of a part containing the minimum amount of material—the smallest possible diameter within the allowable tolerance. Using the same example of a bolt designed to be 10 mm with an allowable tolerance of ± 0.1 mm, the LMC for the bolt would be 9.9 mm (smallest acceptable diameter). The MMC would be 10.1 mm (largest acceptable diameter) for a hole with the same nominal size and tolerance.

Existing researchers have highlighted the importance of metric (M33X1.5 and MJ33X1.5) threads in providing a robust and leak-proof connection [21,22]. They provide a strong and secure connection capable of withstanding the high pressures and mechanical stresses encountered during pump operation. Additionally, threaded connections facilitate straightforward assembly and disassembly, making maintenance, repairs, and part replacements easier without requiring specialized tools.

Threaded connections ensure precise alignment of pump components, which is crucial for maintaining the efficiency and proper functioning of the pump. However, several negative consequences can arise if these threads fail or disengage [4,23,24]. Fluid leaks can occur, reducing pump efficiency and causing potential environmental or safety hazards, particularly if the pumped fluid is hazardous. Pressure loss within the pump system due to disengaged threads can result in decreased performance and failure to meet operational requirements. Mechanical failure is another risk, as misaligned pump components due to loose or failed threads can increase wear and tear, potentially causing significant damage to the pump. Such failures also lead to operational downtime, impacting productivity and increasing costs. In high-pressure systems, the sudden disengagement of threads can pose serious safety risks, including releasing pressurized fluids or gases endangering personnel. Regularly inspecting threaded connections and looking for signs of wear, corrosion, or loosening are essential to prevent such issues. Ensuring threads are tightened to the manufacturer's specified torque values helps avoid under-tightening or over-tightening, which can compromise the connection. Using appropriate thread sealants or Teflon tape enhances sealing capabilities, and employing high-quality threaded components made from suitable materials ensures durability and reliability under operating conditions [25]. These measures collectively help maintain the integrity and performance of the pump system, mitigating the risks associated with thread failure or disengagement.

METHODOLOGY

A 3D CAD model (sectional view) of a pump assembly is shown in Fig. 1(a). CAD modeling was done using Dassault Systèmes Solidworks software. The entire assembly has three components: a barrel, a pump head, and a washer. In all, five CAD models were developed: (a) baseline design-NOM with M33X1.5 threads (design #1), (b) revised design-NOM with M33X1.5 threads (design #2), (c) baseline design-LMC with M33X1.5 threads (design #3), (d) revised design-LMC with M33X1.5 threads (design #4), and (e) revised design-LMC with MJ33X1.5 threads (design #5). M33X1.5 or MJ33X1.5 thread types were used to engage the barrel and pump head. The geometry is cylindrical, and all components are symmetrical about the axis passing through the center of the assembly in the axial direction. Such a model can be modeled as a 2-dimensional plane using asymmetrical boundary conditions about this axis. Accordingly, two 2-dimensional CAD models of a pump assembly with a barrel, pump head, and washer were developed (Fig. 1(b) and (c)). One model represented a baseline design with six threads for engaging the barrel and pump head (Fig. 1(b)). The revised design has five threads to engage the barrel and pump head (Fig. 1(c)). In addition to reducing one thread in the revised design, a larger cutout was made at the base of the pump head. Each model was then designed based on Nominal Material Condition (NOM) and Least Material Condition (LMC). In addition, one more revised design model was developed by replacing M33X1.5 threads with MJ33X1.5. The CAD models were exported as a STEP file for meshing.

Fig. 1 2D CAD model of (a) baseline and (b) revised design of the fuel pump. A 3D sectional view of the revised design of the pump(c)

Each STEP file was imported to the Ansys Mechanical 14.0 software package for finite element modeling and analysis. A pictorial flowchart for the FEA process is given in Fig. 2. The CAD model was cleaned, and meshing was done using 4-nodded quadrilateral elements. Material properties, loading, and boundary conditions were applied as detailed below. Simulation was performed, and stress distributions were computed.

Fig. 2 A standard flowchart of FEA analysis

The FEA model of the pump is given in Fig. 3. Four-nodded quadrilateral elements with variable element sizes were generated. Variable element sizes were selected based on the area of interest and the expected distribution of mechanical stimuli. The mesh size relatively increased away from the threads. To develop the variable mesh size, the CAD model of the pump head was divided into seven parts, denoted as h_1 , h_2 , h_3 , h_4 , h_5 , h_6 , and h_7 . Part h_1 represented the threaded zone. h_6 and h_7 are located at the free edges or are in contact with the washer (w_1). These three parts of the pump head were assigned finer mesh sizes. h_4 denotes a thermal strip in the pump head, which will be used to assign a thermal boundary condition for applying pretension load on the screws in the axial direction.

Similarly, the barrel was divided into five parts, named $b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4,$ and b_5 . b_1 is the threaded portion of the barrel, which has been assigned a finer mesh size of elements. b_5 is in contact with the washer w_1 and was assigned finer mesh sizes. In all, more than 100000 elements and nodes were developed.

Fig. 3 Finite element model of the revised pump assembly

Each material has been assigned material properties in elastic or elastic-plastic regions. The thread and washer were assigned properties until the plastic region. The pump head and barrel material properties were assigned within the elastic region. The material properties in the elastic region of different components are given in Table 1. Fig. 4 shows the material properties of threads and the washer in the plastic region.

Table 1 Material properties in the elastic region of different pump assembly components

Part	Material	Elastic Modulus (GPa)	Density (kg/m ³)	Poisson's ratio	Hardness	Remarks
Pump Head	Steel 17-72A	203	7830	0.32	40	Elastic
Barrel	Steel 52100	200	7800	0.29	60	Elastic
Threads	Steel 52100	200	7850	0.29	53	Elastic-Plastic
Washer	Stainless steel 303	199	8000	0.3	---	Elastic-Plastic

Fig. 4 Material properties of threads and washer in the plastic region

Loading and boundary conditions were applied to the pump assembly, as shown in Fig. 5. The loading conditions were applied in three steps of 1 second each. Load step 1 applied a non-displacement boundary condition (also called SPC) at the base of the pump head, where all nodes' degrees of freedom were set to zero throughout the simulation. A thermal boundary condition was applied to apply a pretension load of 54.747kN on threads in the axial direction. The second step applied the same loading environment (as step 1), except a pressure gradient (maximum value of up to 300MPa) was also applied, thus applying force in the horizontal direction. The third load step was applied to the same loading environment as load step 1. In addition, axisymmetric boundary conditions were assigned to the left-sided boundary for simulating a cylindrical pump assembly. Atmospheric temperature was assigned to be 22°C.

Fig. 5 Loading and boundary conditions applied to different nodes of the FE model

Maximum principal stress and von Mises stress distributions were computed for all models. In all, three Goodman lines were plotted based on the material properties. The first line denotes the boundary for a 50% failure probability to complete 10 million cycles. Then, a safety factor was included by assigning a 5% Coefficient of Variation (COV) to the Ultimate Tensile Strength (UTS) and 8% COV to the fatigue strength. Lastly, a third line with further safety factor was developed considering a surface finish factor (1.6 Ra Derate Factor). The inference of a 5% Coefficient of Variation (COV) of the Ultimate Tensile Strength (UTS) indicates that the standard deviation of the UTS is 5% away from the average UTS. This level of COV suggests that the material's tensile strength is quite consistent and reliable, with minimal fluctuation in its performance under tensile stress. The Surface Finish Derate Goodman Line involves adjusting a material's fatigue strength to account for its surface finish's effects, using the Goodman line to incorporate mean stress impacts. Surface roughness, quantified by Ra values, can significantly influence fatigue performance, with rougher surfaces typically reducing fatigue strength due to the increased likelihood of crack initiation. A derating factor is applied to modify the fatigue strength according to the specified surface roughness in this context.

To plot the Goodman diagram, the σ_m (MPa) was plotted on the x-axis, and σ_a (MPa) was plotted on the y-axis. Three critical lines were plotted: the Mean Goodman Line (red), which indicated a 50% failure rate at 10 million cycles. The 3 Sigma Goodman Line (blue) represented a more conservative estimate with a 5% coefficient of variation (COV) on ultimate tensile strength (UTS) and an 8% COV on fatigue strength (FS). The Surface Finish Derate Goodman Line (green) accounted for surface finish effects with a derate factor of 1.6 times the roughness average (Ra).

The design points—Design #1 (red circle), Design #2 (blue triangle), Design #3 (black square), Design #4 (green diamond), and Design #5 (yellow pentagon)—are plotted on the diagram.

For developing Goodman lines for barrel threads, fatigue strength (8% COV) was 466 MPa, yield strength (7% COV) was 1240 MPa, and UTS (5% COV) was 1510 MPa. Similarly, for developing Goodman lines for pump head threads, fatigue strength (8% COV) was 538 MPa, yield strength (7% COV) was 1480 MPa, and UTS (5% COV) was 1887 MPa. The surface finish for both threads was considered as 3.2Ra.

RESULTS

Barrel threads

Table 2 presents the stress levels experienced by five different barrel thread designs, identified as #1 through #5. For each design, the maximum stress (σ_{max}), minimum stress (σ_{min}), mean stress (σ_m), and alternating stress (σ_a) were provided. Designs #1, #2, and #3 showed relatively lower stress values, suggesting they are safer and more robust under the same conditions. Design #1 has a maximum stress of 916 MPa, a minimum stress of 770 MPa, and a mean stress of 843 MPa. Design #2 has a slightly higher maximum stress of 1014 MPa, a minimum stress of 848 MPa, and a mean stress of 931 MPa. Design #3, with the lowest values among the designs, has a maximum stress of 858 MPa, a minimum stress of 730 MPa, and a mean stress of 794 MPa. Design #3 showed the lowest alternating stress at 64 MPa, suggesting it might perform better against fatigue. In contrast, Design #4 and Design #5 stand out with the highest stress values. Design #4 has the highest maximum stress of 1084 MPa, minimum stress of 910 MPa, and mean stress of 997 MPa. Similarly, Design #5 has a maximum stress of 1050 MPa, minimum stress of 870 MPa, and mean stress of 960 MPa. These high-stress levels indicate that Designs #4 and #5 are weak and require further investigation to ensure they can withstand the loading environment effectively. The alternating stress was highest in Design #5 at 90 MPa, indicating it may be more susceptible to fatigue over time.

This analysis suggested that Designs #1, #2, and #3 are relatively safer and more robust under the given loading conditions. In contrast, with their higher stress levels, Designs #4 and #5 are weaker and require further investigation to address potential weaknesses. The discussion of the Goodman diagram for Design #5 underscores the need to carefully evaluate its fatigue performance to ensure reliability in practical applications.

Table 2 Fatigue failure data, generated from FEA analysis, for designs #1 to #5 for barrel threads

Design	σ_{max} (MPa)	σ_{min} (MPa)	σ_m (MPa)	σ_a (MPa)
#1	916	770	843	73
#2	1014	848	931	83
#3	858	730	794	64
#4	1084	910	997	87
#5	1050	870	960	90

In Design #5, the highest stress was observed on barrel threads at the thread root for each condition (Fig. 6). In load step 1, the pretension load compresses adjacent threads. For example, one barrel thread was compressed with an adjacent pump head thread. In load step 2, the compression was released due to the application of 300 MPa fluid pressure acting opposite to compression. In load step 3, the pressure was released, and thus, stresses increased again. All Stresses in the Barrel were below the -3σ value for yield strength (1240 MPa) except for a very small region where the external thread contacts the internal thread (Fig. 6).

The stresses in this small region were compressive, and the highest tensile stresses were found at the root of the bottom-most thread.

Fig. 6 Von Mises stress distribution at the thread root of the barrel of the pump assembly

The Goodman diagram based on barrel threads designs is given in Fig. 7. Remarkably, all the given points were located below the green Goodman line on the diagram, signifying that the material can endure the specified cyclic loads without failure. This placement in the safe region indicates that the designs are robust against fatigue failure. However, it is essential to note that Design #4, with the highest stress values, was closest to the Goodman line, indicating it is the most critical design among the five and closer to the threshold of potential fatigue failure. Design #5, is close to the limit of the Goodman line but within the safe region. In contrast, Design #1, #2, and #3 are significantly lower than the Goodman line, suggesting a higher safety margin and greater durability under the specified loading conditions.

Fig. 7 Goodman diagram of barrel threads

Pump head threads

Table 3 presented the stress levels experienced by five different pump head thread designs, offering insights into their performance and robustness under operational conditions. Designs #1, #2, and #3 exhibited relatively lower stress values, indicating higher robustness and safety. Specifically, Design #1 had a σ_m of 648 MPa, an σ_a of 84 MPa, a σ_{max} of 732 MPa, and a σ_{min} of 564 MPa. Design #2 showed slightly higher values with a σ_m of 790 MPa, an σ_a of 107 MPa, σ_{max} of 897 MPa, and σ_{min} of 683 MPa. Design #3, the lowest among the designs, had a σ_m of 625 MPa, an σ_a of 71 MPa, σ_{max} of 696 MPa, and σ_{min} of 554 MPa. These lower stress levels and moderate alternating stresses suggested that Designs #1, #2, and #3 were more robust and likely to perform reliably under the given loading conditions for pump head threads.

In contrast, Designs #4 and #5 exhibited significantly higher stress levels, indicating potential weaknesses and a need for further investigation to ensure their reliability. Design #4 had a σ_m of 1198 MPa, an σ_a of 115 MPa, σ_{max} of 1313 MPa, and σ_{min} of 1083 MPa. Similarly, Design #5 showed a σ_m of 1181 MPa, an σ_a of 129 MPa, σ_{max} of 1310 MPa, and σ_{min} of 1052 MPa. These elevated stress levels and higher alternating stresses highlighted the necessity to thoroughly evaluate these designs to address potential vulnerability under operational conditions. Such an assessment was critical for determining their suitability for specific applications, particularly those involving cyclic loads and varying stress conditions.

In Design #5, the highest stresses occurred at the thread roots. Notably, throughout all load steps, the stresses remained below the -3 sigma threshold for yield strength, which is 1480 MPa, ensuring the structural integrity of the pump head under the specified loading conditions (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8 Von Mises stress distribution at the thread root of the pump head

Table 3 values are plotted on a Goodman diagram to assess the safety of materials under cyclic loading conditions (Fig. 9). The Goodman diagram includes a red, blue, and green line, as described above. All design points lie below the green line, denoting that the material can withstand the specified cyclic loads. However, a closer examination reveals that designs #4 and #5, with mean stresses of 1214 MPa and 1166 MPa and alternating stresses of 123 MPa and 125 MPa, respectively, are situated near the green line. This proximity suggests a higher risk of failure for these designs, as they are closer to the material’s fatigue limit. Any slight increase in stress or unexpected variations in material properties could push these points into the unsafe region. On the other hand, designs #1, #2, and #3, with their mean and alternating stresses significantly lower than the green line, indicate a much larger safety margin. Thus, while all designs are deemed safe, designs #4 and #5 necessitate closer monitoring and additional safety considerations due to their higher relative risk.

Table 3 Fatigue failure data, generated from FEA analysis, for designs #1 to 5 for pump head threads

Design	σ_{max} (MPa)	σ_{min} (MPa)	σ_m (MPa)	σ_a (MPa)
#1	732	564	648	84
#2	897	683	790	107
#3	696	554	625	71
#4	1313	1083	1198	115
#5	1310	1052	1181	129

Fig. 9 Goodman diagram of pump head threads

DISCUSSIONS

The FEA conducted on the pump assembly provided insight into the stress distributions under different design configurations and loading conditions. The simulations used five distinct models based on the number of threads, thread type, and NMC or LOM condition.

Comparison of Thread Types and Loading Conditions

The stress analysis revealed that the highest stresses consistently occurred at the thread roots, barrel, and pump head. Notably, the M33X1.5 thread designs exhibited higher stress than the MJ33X1.5 thread designs. The reduction in thread count from six to five in the revised design resulted in a noticeable change in stress distribution. Despite the larger cutout in the revised design, the stresses remained within acceptable limits, indicating the robustness of the revised configuration.

Goodman Diagram Interpretation

The plotted points for all five models indicate that the materials meet the Goodman criterion for fatigue safety. Notably, at barrel threads, Design #4, which exhibited the highest mean stress and alternating stress values, lies closest to the threshold of potential fatigue failure. This suggests that while the design is safe, it is more critical than the others. The position for Design #2 and #5 was similar to Design #4. However, the other two designs (Design #1 and #3) are safe.

In the pump head threads, Designs #1, #2, and #3, with lower mean and alternating stresses, demonstrate a higher safety margin, indicating superior durability under the specified loading conditions. The proximity of designs #4 and #5 to the green Goodman line, which accounts for surface finish effects, suggests a need for careful monitoring and potential additional safety considerations for these designs.

IMPLICATIONS FOR PUMP ASSEMBLY DESIGN

The findings from this study have several implications for the design and optimization of pump assemblies. The use of MJ33X1.5 threads in the revised design has shown to be beneficial in reducing stress concentrations, thereby enhancing the overall durability and reliability of the pump. The stress analysis under LMC conditions provides valuable insights into the worst-case scenarios, ensuring that the pump can withstand extreme operating conditions.

Moreover, the comprehensive evaluation using the Goodman diagram underscores the importance of UTS, fatigue strength, and a surface finish in the design process. Adopting a conservative approach, as represented by the 3 Sigma Goodman Line and the Surface Finish Derate Goodman Line, ensures a robust design capable of enduring cyclic loads without failure.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Despite the comprehensive nature of this study, the study has several limitations. The applied loading conditions were simplified and may only fully encompass some real-world scenarios the pump assembly might encounter, such as dynamic thermal cycles and pressure fluctuations. Material properties were assumed uniform and consistent, which may not reflect real-world material inconsistencies and manufacturing defects. The geometric model was also simplified, excluding features like small fillets, chamfers, and others that could influence stress distribution. The idealized boundary conditions in the simulation differ from actual constraints and support in practical applications, potentially affecting stress distribution and load transfer mechanisms. The fatigue life prediction based on the Goodman diagram relies on certain assumptions about cyclic loading and surface finish effects, which may only partially capture real-world fatigue behavior influenced by loading frequency and environmental conditions.

Future Work Scope

Future work should focus on experimental validation of the FEA results to corroborate the findings from this study. Additionally, exploring alternative thread designs and materials could provide further insights into optimizing the pump assembly for enhanced performance and longevity. Investigating the effects of varying loading conditions, such as thermal cycling and pressure fluctuations, would also contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the pump assembly's behavior.

CONCLUSIONS

This study provided a comprehensive analysis of the mechanical implications of reducing thread engagement in pump assemblies, focusing on understanding the pump barrel-head joints. By utilizing FEA, stress distribution and fatigue performance of two design configurations were analyzed: a baseline with six engagement threads and a revised design with five threads, incorporating both M33X1.5 and MJ33X1.5 thread profiles under nominal (NOM) and least material condition (LMC). The results demonstrated that reducing thread engagement increased stresses, particularly at the thread roots, thereby elevating the risk of fatigue failure. However, optimizing thread geometry, such as using MJ33X1.5 profiles, helped mitigate these adverse effects by enhancing stress distribution and fatigue performance. The Goodman diagram evaluation further highlighted the critical nature of maintaining an adequate number of engaged threads and optimized thread profiles over stringent manufacturing tolerances to ensure reliability. Practically, reducing thread engagement can compromise the reliability and durability of pump assemblies by increasing stresses and reducing fatigue life.

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